

The Impacts of Maiduguri floods and Use of library in Addressing Food and Health Challenges Affecting Households in Maiduguri Metropolitan Council and Jere Local Government Area

Samaila Inuwa, ¹

Aliyu Shehu Yakubu ²

Talatu Rabasa ³

^{1, 2, & 3} Department of Library and Information Science, University of Maiduguri.

¹inuwasamaila24@gmail.com (Corresponding Author)

²kafintafawa2@unimaid.edu.ng

Abstract

Background: This study investigates the Impacts of Maiduguri floods and Use of library in Addressing Food and Health Challenges Affecting Households in Maiduguri Metropolitan Council and Jere Local Government Area, Borno State. Floods, caused by heavy rainfall or dam failures, lead to severe consequences such as displacement, loss of life, and long-term issues like food crises and healthcare challenges.

Method: The study employed a qualitative approach, utilizing interviews to gather data. The objectives were to assess the impact of floods on household food security and health challenges and to explore the role of libraries in providing food and health-related information during floods.

Findings/Results: The findings revealed that floods cause significant displacement and casualties, including deaths from drowning and waterborne diseases like cholera, malaria, and dysentery. Libraries can play a crucial role in addressing these challenges by providing valuable information on agricultural best practices, food storage, and nutrition. They can offer digital resources, online databases, and training sessions to support food security and manage health risks during floods.

Implications: The study highlights the potential of libraries as vital resources in mitigating the impacts of floods on food security and health. By leveraging digital

resources and organizing educational workshops, libraries can significantly support affected communities.

Conclusion: The study concludes that floods have profound and long-lasting effects on communities, particularly in terms of food security and health. Libraries can play a crucial role in addressing these challenges by providing essential information and resources to affected households.

Recommendations: The study recommends that government should improve drainage systems, enhancing flood awareness, and bolstering emergency preparedness to mitigate the impacts of future floods.

Keywords: Floods, Food Security, Health Challenges, Libraries, Household Impact

Introduction: Maiduguri, located in northeastern Nigeria, has experienced flooding in the past due to heavy rainfall, poor drainage systems, and the region's geographical vulnerability. Floods can have significant and multifaceted impacts on household food security and health. On September 11, 2024, Maiduguri and Jere serve as the hub for the responses to the humanitarian crisis in the northeast. The crisis was caused by the rupture of the Alau dam on the Ngadda River, 20 kilometres (12 miles) south of Maiduguri over the weekend. According to National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA), more than 23,000 households, and upwards of 150,000 people, were hit by the subsequent rapid rise of waters. People affected by floods are escorted through flood water on a military boat in Maiduguri on September 12, 2024.

Floods are among the most devastating natural disasters, causing widespread destruction to infrastructure, agriculture, and livelihoods. They disrupt ecosystems, displace communities, and exacerbate food insecurity and health challenges, particularly in vulnerable households. The aftermath of flooding often leads to contaminated water supplies, the spread of waterborne diseases, and the destruction of crops, which can severely impact food availability and nutrition. In such crises, access to accurate information, resources, and community support becomes critical for recovery and resilience.

Libraries, often regarded as community hubs of knowledge and learning, play a vital role in addressing these challenges. By providing access to information on disaster preparedness, health guidelines, and sustainable agricultural practices. Libraries

empower individuals and households to mitigate the effects of floods. Additionally, libraries can serve as centers for disseminating critical health information, connecting communities with relief services, and fostering educational programs that promote long-term resilience. In this context, libraries emerge as essential institutions in combating the food and health challenges exacerbated by floods, ensuring that households have the tools and knowledge needed to recover and thrive in the face of adversity.

Severe flooding in the Northeastern Nigerian city of Maiduguri has claimed some lives and forced thousands of people from their homes, severely damaging hospitals and triggering a growing health crisis, according to a statement from the Unique Care and Support Foundation, CASFOD. The livestock and agricultural sectors have been severely impacted, leaving farmers without income or food. Over 70% of vulnerable families benefiting from their livestock livelihood program have lost livestock, exacerbating the crisis. Collective efforts are essential to prevent further suffering and ensure a swift recovery for Borno State's most vulnerable populations. Libraries can play a crucial role in addressing the food and health challenges affecting households in Maiduguri and Jere.

Statement of the Problem

Maiduguri, the capital of Borno State, Nigeria, has experienced recurrent floods disasters in multifaceted form resulting in significant social, economic, environmental consequences including displacement and migration of communities, damage of infrastructure, agriculture and industry, increased risk of waterborne diseases and mental health issues, and loss of human life and livelihood. The growing vulnerability of Maiduguri's residents to these challenges highlights the need for innovative approaches to mitigate the impacts of floods. Libraries, as community knowledge hubs, have the potential to play a crucial role in addressing these issues. However, their capacity to do so remains largely underutilized. The problem lies in the lack of integration of library resources into disaster response and household resilience-building strategies. This research seeks to explore the impacts of Maiduguri floods and the roles of libraries in addressing food and health challenges affecting households in Maiduguri, focusing on their capacity to enhance awareness, provide actionable knowledge, and foster community resilience in the face of recurrent floods.

Research Objectives

The objectives of this study are to:

1. To assess the impact of floods on household in Maiduguri and Jere Local Government area
2. To explore the use of library in addressing food challenges affecting household in Maiduguri Metropolitan and Jere Local Government area
3. To explore the use of library in addressing health challenges during flood disaster in Maiduguri and Jere.

Literature review

This article is informed by theoretical framework phenomenology and hermeneutics of Smith, J.A., Flowers, P., & Larkin, M. (2009). It focuses on human experience, meaning and interpretation. It requires to describe phenomena as they are experienced without predetermined assumptions. The theory is appropriate for in-depth exploration of people's experiences related to specific life events or challenges. Phenomenology can be utilized to understand how individuals and communities experience floods. This involves the immediate sensory experiences and the emotional responses such as fear, loss of life and properties as well as resilience. Hermeneutics is a method for interpreting texts but was expanded by philosophers to include the interpretation of human experiences and cultural phenomena. Hermeneutics can be applied to understand how people interpret the meaning of floods. For instance, others may see floods as natural disasters, while others may interpret them through religious or cultural lenses e.g. as divine punishment or a test of faith. A theoretical framework of phenomenology and Hermeneutics approach expands our understanding of floods beyond physical damage, revealing existential, cultural, and ethical dimensions. This framework can inform disaster response, policy making, and psychological recovery by centering human experience and meaning making.

Theoretical framework phenomenology and Hermeneutics

The Maiduguri flood of 2024 was a devastating natural disaster that severely impacted the city of Maiduguri, and Jere, Nigeria. The flooding was caused by heavy rainfall and the collapse of the Alau Dam, resulting in significant loss of life, displacement of residents, and widespread damage to infrastructure.

Raphael Ane Atanga & Vitus Tankpa (2021) wrote a paper on climate change, flood disasters impacts and food security nexus in northern Ghana. The paper highlight the impacts of climate change include flood disasters which in turn affect food production with subsequent impact on food security. While climate change impact can be positive in some regions, it can be negative in other regions as it could lead to excess or lack of water, which negatively affects food production. Most especially, flood disasters have reportedly become frequent with devastating consequences on food production. However, their paper only assess the impact of flood on food security but failed to assess the health challenges affecting households.

In a paper written by Kumar, V., Sharma, K. V., Caloiero, T., Mehta, D. J., & Singh, K. (2023) titled “Comprehensive Overview of Flood Modeling Approaches: A Review of Recent Advances.” The study provides a thorough summary of flood modeling’s current condition, problems, and probable future directions. The study of flood modeling includes models based on hydrologic, hydraulic, numerical, rainfall-runoff, remote sensing and GIS, artificial intelligence and machine learning, and multiple-criteria decision analysis. Additionally, it covers the heuristic and metaheuristic techniques employed in flood control. The weakness of their paper with regards to my paper is that it did not address the use of library in addressing food and health challenges during floods as well as the impacts of floods.

According to Aldardasawi, A. M., & Eren, B. (2021) in their paper titled “Floods and their impact on the environment” indicated that resources like air and water are present in the Ecosystem for the benefit of biological life, but a slight disturbance in them results in catastrophic calamities; the flood is one of them. Floods are wrecking threats not only to the life of the individuals but also result in long-term destructions to the economy, environment, and the psychological state of the affected individuals.

Umar, N., & Gray, A. (2023) in their paper “Flooding in Nigeria: a review of its occurrence and impacts and approaches to modelling flood data” revealed that their paper surveys flood mapping and modelling in Nigeria in regard to frequency and impact of floods in the last decade. Their aim was to understand the frequency and patterns of flooding and approaches to its modelling in relation to current practices globally. According to them, the northern part of Nigeria is affected more by flooding than the south, so should be prioritized for flood management. The use of remote sensing data with GIS techniques is the most common approach to flood modelling in Nigeria. Bayesian and machine learning approaches should be used, in preference to process-based models. Similarly, Feng, B., Zhang, Y., & Bourke, R. (2021) in their paper titled “Urbanization impacts on flood risks based on urban growth data and coupled flood models” disclosed that Urbanization increases regional impervious surface area, which generally reduces hydro logic response time and therefore increases flood risk. The objective of this work is to investigate the sensitivities of urban flooding to urban land growth through simulation of flood flows under different urbanization conditions and during different flooding stages.

Reed, C., Anderson, W., Kruczkiwicz, A., Nakamura, J., Gallo, D., Seager, R., & McDermid, S. S. (2022) found out that recent record rainfall and flood events have prompted increased attention to flood impacts on human systems. Information regarding

flood effects on food security is of particular importance for humanitarian organizations and is especially valuable across Africa's rural areas that contribute to regional food supplies. They quantitatively evaluate where and to what extent flooding impacts food security across Africa, using a Granger causality analysis and panel modeling approaches.

Cowen and Delmotte (2020) in their paper Ostrom, Floods and Mismatched Property Rights indicated that traditional approaches to institutional analysis suggest that flood management is either a public good that only the government is competent to provide or a private good to which individual landowners are ultimately responsible for supplying. They argue that an important cause of failure in flood management is mismatched property rights. This is where the scale of natural events and resources fail to align with the scale of human activities, responsibility and ownership. Moreover, the spatial dimensions of floods mean that their management is often appropriately conceptualized as a common pool resource problem. As a result, commons institutions as conceptualized and observed by Elinor Ostrom (2015) are likely to be major contributors to effective flood management. What governance process should decide the size and scope of these institutions? The authors of this paper argue that bottom-up responses to problems of mismatched property rights are facilitated within larger societies that are characterized by market processes. Moreover, the wider presence of price signals delivers to local communities' essential knowledge about the cost of maintaining private property and the relative scarcity of the communal goods. They discuss how their theoretical positions align with experience in Britain and what the implications of our theoretical approach are for facilitating the development of better institutions.

Methodology

Qualitative research method was employed for the research. The underlying assumption is that the qualitative method display a different approach to scholarly inquiry than the method of quantitative research. The researchers employed qualitative method to collect data through interviews with the displaced persons and the librarians. Purposive sampling was employed to select the participants of the study. The inclusion criteria is that they must have been victims of the 2024 Maiduguri flood disaster and the librarians who experienced the devastating flood and have specialized in information dissemination especially e-resources. Non victims of the 2024 Maiduguri flood were excluded from the study.

Data Analysis

Qualitative data was analyzed with an interpretative phenomenological approach to explore themes and develop core variables to describe Maiduguri and Jere floods and use of library in addressing food and health challenges affecting households in Maiduguri and Jere local government areas. AUM, RMT and DPS are assigned to represent the interviewees of this research.

The data were organized by generating open, axial and selective coding that are converted into groups and themes. Emerging themes from the interview are presented according to the research questions developed. In line with the purposive sampling technique, eight participants were interviewed, the data collected through interviews, was analyzed without losing focus of its richness, and that is the importance of qualitative research.

Step 1: Manual review and reflection

The first step of data analysis as earlier mentioned above was a manual review and reflection, which include data collected from all the four respondents. The researcher analyzed data from the interview after the transcription. The main reason was to find out themes, which were revealed by the participants. At first, the researchers listened attentively to the interviews recorded and read the transcripts many times. The researcher read, edited, and checked the data, paragraph by paragraph, for accuracy, the checking was done manually.

Step 2: Open coding:

In order to create wisdom of the phenomenon under study as revealed by the participants, the researcher gets engaged with the data as much as possible by reading the transcribed transcript number of times. The participants allowed the researcher to transcribed the interview verbatim. Thus, at the open coding stage, units of analysis were used to identify statements within the transcribed texts that matched or connect to the study objectives. The interpretative nature of the analysis necessitates the recording of quotes and ideas considered unique or interesting and those describing the study participants during the interview process. The ideas were open coded into several emerging themes. Under this provisional coding stage, anything connected to the research objectives/questions was recorded.

Step three: Axial coding:

Axial coding involves detecting relationships among the open codes. The axial coding logically linked open coded statements. It is at this step that connection is established between statements to reduce a wide variety of data sets into conceptual categories. Accordingly, the minor themes were clustered into major ones. This stage is the most tasking, yet it establishes a close interaction between the researcher and the text. Emerging nodes created at the open coding stage are grouped under another code at the axial coding stage development to reflect the research objectives and questions

Step four: Selective coding:

At this stage, the researchers identify the core variable that comprises all of the data. The researcher then reread the transcripts and selectively codes any data that relates to the core variable identified. At this stage, the connection is established between emerging themes. Coded statements conveying similar meanings or concept are grouped under a descriptive label called child nodes. The final phase involves the compilation of emerging themes from the first, second through the last coded documents. This is carried out through identification of predominant higher order themes.

Step five: Data interpretations

The third phase of the analysis in this study identified categories or themes, which were able to offer answers to the research questions. Therefore, I proceed with the data interpretation. In comparison with the emerging themes from open coding to axial coding in the second stage, this process was more analytical and theoretical. It is aimed at finding linkages among the broad conceptual categories, and choose from the themes that emerged from the earlier analyses.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher must understand the concept of research ethics before conducting research. Data collection methods in specific research will probe their secrets and emotions and impinge on their rights, their privacy, and their consent. Since the data collected from the subjects may be private and confidential, it cannot be exposed to others as it may adversely affect not only the subjects but associated with the subjects. These strategies suggested by (Creswell, 2013) are employed in this research:

- (a) The research objectives are articulated verbally and in writing so that they are clearly understood by the informants, including a description of how data will be used.
- (b) Permission to proceed with the study as articulated was gotten from the informants.
- (c) Using coded references to protect the anonymity of the participants.
- (d) Informants were informed of all data collection devices and activities.
- (e) The informant’s rights and interest were considered first when choices are made regarding reporting the data.
- (f) The final decision regarding informant anonymity rest with the informant.

On this note, the researcher explained the nature of the research to the respondents in order to clarify, assured them of their total confidentiality, and develops their trust. Their identity and the data collected will only be used for academic purpose. The entire participants were guaranteed of confidentiality and of their right to withdraw at any time of the research, for any purpose, devoid of penalties. The reason for the research was explicitly explained to participants both in writing and verbally.

Results.

The results identified three major themes. These include: (a) impact of Maiduguri floods (b) use of library in addressing food challenges (c) use of library in addressing health challenges.

Table 1. Impact of Maiduguri floods

Themes	Code	Responses
Impact of Maiduguri floods	DPS 2	Floods have already displaced people, leading to internal displacement and overcrowded temporary shelters.
	DPS 1	Survivors experienced psychological trauma from losing loved ones, homes, and livelihoods.
	DPS 4	Floods have their own casualties, which include loss of life due to drowning, collapsing structures, or waterborne diseases.
	RMT 1	The health risk of floods is that they increase the risk of waterborne diseases like cholera, malaria, and dysentery due to contaminated water and poor sanitation.

DPS 2	Roads, bridges, and buildings have been damaged or destroyed, disrupting transportation and communication.
DPS 3	Markets and businesses were forced to close, leading to economic losses.
AUM 2	Maiduguri floods have altered the landscapes of Maiduguri and Jere, destroyed habitats, and led to soil erosion.
RMT 2	Floodwaters often carry pollutants, debris, and waste, contaminating water sources. The College of Agriculture library is completely submerged by water.

Table 2. Use of library in addressing food challenges

Themes	Code	Responses
Use of library in addressing food challenges	AUM 1	Libraries can provide important information on agricultural best practices, food storage, and nutritional education. This knowledge will assist households in making better decisions about food production and consumption, even during floods.
	RMT 2	Libraries can offer digital resources and online databases to educate flood victims, providing up-to-date information on weather patterns, market trends, and innovative farming techniques, thereby supporting agricultural productivity and food security.
	RMT1	Libraries can organize training sessions and workshops focused on sustainable agriculture, food preservation, and nutrition. These programs can empower communities with practical skills to enhance food security.
	AUM 2	Libraries can partner with non-governmental organizations and government agencies to disseminate critical information on food aid programs, agricultural subsidies, and emergency relief efforts to affected households.
	AUM 1	Libraries can serve as distribution points for seeds, tools, and other agricultural inputs provided by aid organizations, ensuring that flood-affected households have access to the resources they need to sustain their food production.

Table 3. Use of library in addressing health challenges

Theme	Code	Responses
Use of library in addressing health challenges	AUM 2	Libraries can provide fliers and online services (e.g., databases, e-books) to educate flood victims with up-to-date information on diseases, treatments, and prevention strategies.
	AUM 2	Libraries can organize workshops and symposiums to train individuals on how to find, understand, and use health information effectively during floods.
	AUM 2	Libraries can connect individuals to mental health resources, such as counseling services and support groups.
	RMT 2	Libraries can collaborate with healthcare workers to organize health fairs, offering screenings for conditions like malaria, typhoid, and diarrhea.
	AUM 1	Libraries can organize programs on topics such as nutrition, cholera, and chronic disease management, and partner with hospitals/clinics to provide resources.

1. Impact of Maiduguri Floods.

Participants of the study were interviewed about the floods that occurred in Maiduguri and its impacts on the residents of Maiduguri and Jere local government area. According to the participants of the study, floods have impacts that caused displacement of residents from their areas. DPS 2 in his own verbatim words in Hausa language stated that *“Mallam tunda nake, ban tabba gani irin wannan ambaliya ba. Ruwa ya kori mutanie sun gudu sun koma en gudun hijra”* Meaning in English *“Mallam I have never seen this type of flood. Floods have already displaced people from their various residencies, forcing people to run away from their homes, leading to internal displacement and overcrowded temporary shelters”*. DPS 4 on the other hand stated and I quoted verbatim *“Ambaliya yamna da nashi rawni, ya jawo mutuwan mutuwan mutani diyawa, fadiwan gidaje da kuma citutuka. Meaning that “that floods have its own causalities which include loss of life due to drowning, collapsing structures, or waterborne diseases. The participants further revealed that the health risk of floods was that it increased risk of waterborne diseases like cholera, malaria, and dysentery due to contaminated water and poor sanitation.”* Furthermore, the data collected revealed the impacts of floods on economic activities. Many of the participants of the study indicated the impact of floods on agriculture. They stated that

floods can destroy crops, livestock, and farmland, leading to food shortages and loss of livelihoods for farmers. The data also disclosed **the impacts of flood on infrastructure. RMT 1 disclosed that** roads, bridges, and buildings have been damaged or destroyed, disrupting transportation and communication. Similarly, DPS 2 and 4 were of the opinion that markets and businesses were forced to close, leading to economic losses. Meanwhile, DPS 3 stated that Maiduguri floods have altered landscapes of Maiduguri and Jere, it has destroyed habitats, and led to soil erosion. One the participants (AUM 2) also informed the researchers that floodwaters often carry pollutants, debris, and waste, contaminating water sources. In his own words: *as I am speaking to you now, the situations people find themselves here are terrible. Look at college of Agric library, is completely submerged by water.*

A significant proportion of the data reported on the social and psychological effects, vulnerable groups and food insecurity. According to DPS 1 and 2, with regards to social and psychological effects, survivors experienced psychological trauma from losing loved ones, homes, and livelihoods. Similarly, in terms of vulnerable groups, the data indicated that certain groups are disproportionately affected by floods especially women and children. They faced higher risks of malnutrition and health complications. The elderly and disabled ones struggled to evacuate or access relief services. Low income people have less resources to pull through from losses and are more likely to experience food insecurity.

2. Use of Library in Addressing Food Challenges Affecting Households in Maiduguri and Jere local Government Areas.

Participants of this study revealed information about the Maiduguri floods and use of library in addressing food and health challenges affecting households in Maiduguri and Jere local government area. AUM 1 in an interview with the researchers indicated that libraries can give an important information on agricultural best practices, food storage, and nutritional education. This knowledge will assist households take better decisions about food production and consumption, even during flood. In his own words “let me tell you without fear of contradiction that our library can provide information on agricultural best practices, food storage, and nutritional education.” Similarly, RMT 2 was of the opinion that libraries can offer digital resources and online databases that provide up-to-date information on weather patterns, market trends, and innovative farming techniques, thereby supporting agricultural productivity and food security. On the other hand RMT 1 informed the researchers that libraries can organize training sessions and workshops focused on sustainable agriculture, food preservation, and nutrition. These programs can

empower communities with practical skills to enhance food security. AUM 2 informed the researchers that libraries can partner with non-governmental organizations and government agencies to disseminate critical information on food aid programs, agricultural subsidies, and emergency relief efforts to affected households. Based on the data collected, AUM 2 and RMT 1 gave similar opinion that libraries can serve as community centers where people can meet, share information, and support each other. In a related development, the data collected disclosed that libraries can play a role in conducting research and collecting data on local food security issues, which can inform policy decisions and targeted interventions to address food challenges in flood affected areas. AUM 1 told the researchers that libraries can serve as distribution points for seeds, tools, and other agricultural inputs provided by aid organizations, ensuring that flood affected households can have access to the resources they need to sustain their food production.

3. Use of library in Addressing Health Challenges Affecting Households in Maiduguri and Jere local Government Areas.

In terms of using libraries during health changes due to devastating flood, the data collected revealed that libraries can play crucial roles in addressing various health challenges during flood scenario. The data revealed that libraries can provide access to credible health information sources like books, journals, and databases. AUM 2 stated that library can provide online services to educated flood victims such as databases and e-books for up-to-date information on diseases, treatments, and prevention strategies. Moreover, AUM 2 in his own words unveiled that *“we can organize workshops and symposiums to provide training on how to find, understand, and use health information effectively during flood.”* Similarly, the data collected revealed that libraries can offer access to research articles, clinical trials, and other scholarly materials for researchers and healthcare professionals. According to the interviewees, librarians can assist researchers in getting relevant information, conducting literature reviews, and using databases efficiently. RMT 2 said that libraries can collaborate with healthcare workers to organize health fairs, offering screenings for various health conditions like malaria, typhoid, diarrhea and many others. On the other hand, AUM 1 stated that libraries can organize programs on topics such as nutrition, cholera and long-lasting disease management. The library can equally partner with hospitals, clinics, and community health centers to provide resources and services to patients and the public. Similarly, the data collected revealed that library can play role in terms of medical health support. RM 1 revealed that libraries provide quiet spaces for individuals to relax, read, and de-stress.

While AUM 2 stated that libraries can connect individuals to mental health resources, such as counseling services and support groups. In another development, the data revealed some challenges with regards to impact on health. According to AUM 2, while libraries have a significant impact on health, there are challenges facing the libraries such as funding constraints, limited budgets and the implementation of programs. Similarly, RMT 1 stated that technological barriers, access to digital resources and online services may be limited for those in underserved communities as some of the challenges facing the libraries.

Discussion

Floods are among the most devastating natural disasters, with far-reaching impacts on households, particularly in terms of food security and health. These challenges are often exacerbated in vulnerable communities, where resources and infrastructure are limited. Libraries, often overlooked in disaster response, can play a critical role in addressing these challenges by providing access to information, resources, and community support. The goal in conducting this research was to identify the impact of Maiduguri floods and how library can be used to address food and health challenges Affecting households in Maiduguri and Jere local government area. The data shows that **floods have impacts that caused displacement of residents from their areas as well as** loss of life due to drowning, collapsing structures, or waterborne diseases. This is in line with the paper of Reed, C., Anderson, W., Kruczkiewicz, A., Nakamura, J., Gallo, D., Seager, R., & McDermid, S. S. (2022). Their research found out that recent record rainfall and flood events have prompted increased attention to flood impacts on human systems. Information regarding flood effects on food security is of particular importance for humanitarian organizations and is especially valuable across Africa's rural areas that contribute to regional food supplies. They quantitatively evaluate where and to what extent flooding impacts food security across Africa, using a Granger causality analysis and panel modeling approaches.

In terms of use of library in addressing food challenges during flood, the data confirms that libraries can give an important information on agricultural best practices, food storage, and nutritional education. This knowledge will assist households take better decisions about food production and consumption, even during flood. The data found that apart from giving information on agricultural best practice, library can also organize training sessions and workshops focused on sustainable agriculture, food preservation, and nutrition. These programs can empower communities with practical skills to enhance food security.

Libraries can also partner with non-governmental organizations and government agencies to disseminate critical information on food aid programs, agricultural subsidies, and emergency relief efforts to affected households. These roles of libraries during flood is in contrast with the paper of Kumar, V., Sharma, K. V., Caloiero, T., Mehta, D. J., & Singh, K. (2023) titled “Comprehensive Overview of Flood Modeling Approaches: A Review of Recent Advances.” Their paper provides a thorough summary of flood modeling’s current condition, problems, and probable future directions.

With regards to use of library in addressing health challenges, the data enumerated some roles that library can play during flood to address health challenges. These roles among other things include provision of access to credible health information sources like books, journals, and databases, provision of online services such as databases and e-books for up-to-date information on diseases, treatments, and prevention strategies, hosting of workshops and programs to teach individuals how to find, understand, and use health information effectively during flood, offering access to research articles, clinical trials, and other scholarly materials for researchers and healthcare professionals, organize programs on topics such as nutrition, cholera and long-lasting disease management. The library can equally partner with hospitals, clinics, and community health centers to provide resources and services to patients and the public.

Conclusion

Floods pose significant challenges to food security and health, particularly for vulnerable households. Libraries, as community-centered institutions, can play a transformative role in addressing these challenges by providing access to critical information, resources, and support systems. Integrating libraries into disaster response plans can ensure that households have the tools and knowledge they need to overcome food and health challenges in the aftermath of floods. The results of the study established that floods had serious impacts on the residents of Maiduguri and Jere local government areas. Furthermore, libraries can play vital roles in addressing food challenges as well as health challenges during flood disaster.

Recommendations:

The study recommends that government should improve drainage systems, enhancing flood awareness, and encouraging emergency preparedness to mitigate the impacts of future floods.

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